

ELIXIR Commissioned Service Report for Deliverables/Milestones

Document info

Title	Review and update of the assessment metrics
Deliverable/Milestone Number	M2.1
Responsible Participant	Nina Norgren - SE-UU/NBIS
WP Number	2
Dissemination level	PU

Version history

Version	Revised by	Date	Comment
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	Admin Check by Hub (CoS Portfolio Manager)		

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

(Remove if not applicable)

TMD	Training Metrics Database

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Executive Summary

The milestone M2.1 is part of WP2: *Consolidating the Training Platform Infrastructure (services and resources)*. Its objective is to review and update the ELIXIR core assessment metrics used in the Training Metrics Database (TMD).

The aim of this milestone was to produce an updated set of ELIXIR core survey questions to better align with the evolving needs of training activities across nodes. These updated questions will eventually be implemented in the TMD

The improved core question set will enhance the consistency and impact of data collected through training surveys, ensuring better analysis and reporting on training activities across ELIXIR.

Presentation Overview

This milestone focuses on updating the ELIXIR core survey questions used within the TMD. The core questions cover three areas:

1. Demographic Questions: Collecting participant backgrounds.
2. Quality Questions: Measuring satisfaction with course structure and content.
3. Impact Questions: Assessing short- and long-term training benefits.

The questions can be used in different surveys in connection to training events, with the intent of collecting and aggregating statistics of courses, both within nodes and across all of Elixir.

With this milestone we aimed at updating the core questions, to better fit the current environment of training within our nodes.

The process

All core questions were collected in a document, where space was given for nodes to write their feedback. In a first instance, all Training coordinators were emailed with the request to provide feedback on the existing questions, and if there were any questions missing. After the deadline, the TMD working group (open to anyone), used the feedback to make updates/changes to the questions. This could range from slight rewording of some questions, to adding new options to other questions. Once we had drafted this updated set of questions, we again emailed all Training coordinators requesting their feedback on the updated set. With this final feedback we then made the last few updates to the questions, and finalized the new set of core questions.

The resulting Elixir core question set

The feedback and updates for every question can be found here:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1FbWK5OLwR1Th_dcAjVCA_6CksC136OT_HLPbYxsTpQc/edit?tab=t.o#heading=h.01fk1vbh4ura

Once the new TMD model has been launched, this new updated core question set will be launched for use by the nodes (part of M2.2)

Outcomes and Impacts of the deliverable

The updated Elixir core questions improve the relevance and consistency of training data collected across nodes, ensuring a more accurate and comprehensive understanding of training activities. The updated questions will provide better insights into training impact, and better fit today's trainings.